

Ameliorate Student-Teacher Relationship through Spirituality

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ABSTRACT

Teachers are the role models of the students. To provide quality education is the great responsibility of a teacher. They not only guide them in their studies but in all round development and even in shaping their career. Students expect a lot from their teachers. Due to change in the system of the society, education system is also changing. Some new trends are into existence. The relationship between teacher and a student has taken a drastic turn. It is deteriorating day by day. This chaos in the relationship is not one sided but is occurring due to the flaws that have been into the presence at both the sides. In earlier times such scenario was not there. Students used to respect their teachers and teachers were completely devoted towards their duty. The education was carried out under the shade of trees. Guru- Shishya relation was pious. This bounding was made possible because there was a spiritual environment all around. Crime rate was also up to its minimal level that too because of the moral ethics within the students and teachers as well. To curb this problem one needs to have a deep insight of both the perspectives and it can be curtailed with the support of spirituality.

Keywords: *Education, Spiritual, Perspectives, relationship and management*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays the news of bad reputation of either a teacher or a student is always in the air. As said change is the law of nature so changes are inevitable no matter whatever field of life it may be. These changes are increasing day by day and they have taken hold of all spheres of life. Educational

institutions are not unaffected by these changes. Especially the pious student-teacher relationship has gone under tremendous change. A teacher in primitive times was considered 'guru', a person who not only enlightens the lives of his pupils or 'shishya but also embodies the ethics and values that a pupil wishes to assimilate. A guru was considered a person who used to infuse great ideology and strengthens the walls of belief, thought, and above all- wisdom. In real sense a real teacher is the one who lends a proper culture and set of values to his students. Teacher's teachings encompass all spheres of life and impart universal principles taking into consideration all religions which weave the entire fabric of our life. In olden times, teacher student relationship used to sum up total devotion, awe, respect and adoration. This relationship has considered as the most sustainable and has acquired supreme position. So, there is an hour to have a brief overview of this deterioration situation which needs to be rectified.

PRESENT STATUS OF STUDENT-TEACHER RELATIONSHIP

Young and inexperienced teachers who are new to the profession try to prove that they have a good contact with students so they become too friendly with them. They make an effort to gain approval and acceptance from student ultimately leading to poor classroom management. The whole class scenario is disturbed by a single shameless act by the teacher's side. Students loose respect for them and ultimately step down to an unacceptable behavior. Nowadays there is a new trend of posting homework and assignments through social media; even this facility is either misused by a teacher or a student by sending improper messages to each

other as there is no supervision over social media. They rather than making use of the innovations are making it a curse on the society

Students nowadays have rightly or wrongly assumed that teachers don't care about them and have no interest in their career or their studies. Whether they pass or fail in their examinations is none of a teacher's business. Students' trust in their teachers is shackled down and sometimes they seek extra help from somewhere else. Students become uncooperative and start misbehaving in their classrooms.

News about teachers and students being involved in physical relationship is at the hike. Most of the cases end up in the criminal cases where legal actions are taken against either of the side. Students have become so violating that they even charge a case against the teachers if they slap a child even if it is just a sort of pat at the back. They even forget that like parents their teachers too have a kind of right on them, they can slap them with a supportive gesture too.

DOORS OF SPIRITUALITY

“A child teaches itself. But you can help it to go forward in its own way. What you can do, is not of the positive nature, but of the negative. You can take away the obstacles, but knowledge comes out of its own nature. Loosen the soil a little, so that it may come out easily. Put a hedge round it; see that it is not killed by anything, and there your work stops. You cannot do anything else. The rest is manifestation from within its own nature” - **Swami Vivekanandaji**

This vary thought is missing today. A teacher should implement it. He should focus on the negative aspect of the student. His task is improving the student's personality not to kill it through insensible means. Spirituality can teach a lot to the human beings. It can open a new and transformed gateway for every individual. The teachings from spiritual books or by spiritual personalities can bring a revolution to the existing scenario. In this world of fret-fume and trial-tribulation, spirituality can put a peaceful hand forth. Every person whether a teacher or a student has to face the result of his actions. He is responsible for his destiny. If teacher and student are facing the problem of relationship today than that is created by them only and they can only uproot it. Buddha ji said:

“Every human being is the author of his own health or disease”

Spirituality opens the door to positive thinking. Spiritualism's main focus is to promote an individual's personal experience with God and when you are connected with God, you cannot attempt any wrong deed in life. God is the ultimate reality. When such concepts are made clearer to the students and teachers, may be they can divert their bad mindset to the path of honesty and righteousness. It teaches the man to stay calm and quiet. It gives the lesson of meditation. Religious books can help to soothe the behavior of mankind. Spiritual teachings can transform a person's personality. It can teach him that your spirit is all that is going to remain the same at the end of this life on other hand the body is destructive. We all have a lot to do with our body only; we are less bothered about the nourishment of our soul. One should know the actual reality. Students should be taught the lesson of respect and gratefulness. They should be made understood that their teachers are just like their parents and same should be made clear to teachers that the students are not less than kids. Actually this whole world has become chaotic. We all need some stability in our lives in all the spheres. Spiritualism can boost our lost moral character. The chapters about old classroom teachings should be made available in the libraries of educational institutions. The students should inculcate a sort of true finding for his life builder in the guise of a teacher and teacher should try to set example for the other teachers.

Upanishads teaches us that we all are born one single God and all beings will merge at the time of complete dissolution of the universe. To quote:

आनन्दं ब्रह्मेति व्यजानात् ।
आनन्दाद्ध्येव खल्विमानि भूतानि जायन्ते ।
आनन्दो जातनि जीवन्ति ।
आनन्दं प्रयन्त्यभिसंविशन्ति ॥ (तै.)

(Taitariya Upanishad)

Krishna says in the Bhagavad Gita, "I am the ultimate goal of the all the souls. I am their protector. I grace them with divine knowledge and love. I am their loving supreme God. I am the observer of the actions of the souls. All the souls reside in Me; I am their ultimate refuge when they humbly surrender to Me." (Bhagavad Gita, 9/18)

Every human being in this universe is boosting about himself. A teacher is proud to be a teacher and a student feels he is giving fees for whatever he is gaining from the teacher. This quote can remind them

that there is nothing above God in this world that one should be proud of. He is observing the actions of all single being. One should mend his tasks. There is no one who can teach anybody. The teacher spoils everything by thinking that he is teaching. Thus Vedanta says that within man is all knowledge—even in a boy it is so—and it requires only an awakening, and that much is the work of a teacher. On the other hand students have forgotten the human values and respect for teachers. They should remind of the thoughts like:

“Gurur-Brahmaa Gurur-Visnunar-Gururdevo
Maheshvarah
Gurureva Param Brahma Tasmai Shrii-Gurave
Namah”
- Guru Stotra-

It means that the Guru is Brahma, the Guru is Vishnu, the Guru Deva is Maheswara (Shiva), The Guru is Verily the Para-Brahman (Supreme Brahman); Salutations to that Guru. They should take their teacher as their God rather than misbehaving with them.

CONCLUSION

Spirituality can really improve the above stated scenario. The students should be taught chapters on spirituality. Though Spiritual or moral education is the part of syllabus at elementary level but actually it should be made mandatory through all course work. It is not that it should be one of those subjects to be tested out through examination system but its practical knowledge should be imparted. At least one lecture in a week can be given to the students and there could be open discussions where student teacher relationship could be tied in a spiritual knot. This will add such a moment in student's institutional activity that will only focus on the problems to be solved out if that occurs at any end and even both can relax and have a deep insight into the religious, spiritual and moral thoughts. Thoughts of every students and teacher should be welcomed. This may put an end to the mess created in the world between student and teacher relationship. Government should even plan campaigns that carry on spiritual events. Social medial should promote spiritual thoughts. Such activities can bring a sound relationship of teacher-student into existence. When this relationship is improved the rest of the relationships on the earth can be improved itself.

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